

Upload guide to zenodo for the HEPI project

This how to is intended to guide you through uploading and annotating digital objects, such as training material, project reports and other relevant resources to [zenodo](#).

The steps will be very similar for different types of objects and different projects, but are presented here tailored for the HEPI project.

If you want to learn more about zenodo please consult the official [zenodo documentation](#).

You can also test everything in the [zenodo sandbox without risk](#) (beware that the information you share there might still get public).

Step 0 - Register

If you do not have an official zenodo account yet, please [sign up first](#). You can also reuse your existing GitHub, ORCID or OpenAIRE account. You will have to verify your email address.

If you do not have an ORCID yet, this might be also a good timepoint [to obtain one](#). You can crosslink your [accounts also later](#).

zenodo

Research. Shared! Sign up today

Citeable. Discoverable

Uploads get a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) to make them easily and uniquely citeable.

Communities

Accept or reject uploads to your own community (e.g workshops, EU projects, institutions or entire disciplines).

Trusted Research Data Management

Built on top of CERN's expertise in managing 100s of petabytes of research data from the Large Hadron Collider.

Sign up with GitHub

Sign up with ORCID

Sign up with OpenAIRE

— OR —

Username

Full name

Affiliations

Email Address

Please use an institutional email address

Password

Sign up

Step 1 - Sign up

Please [sign in with your existing account](#) (or the account created in Step 0)

Step 2 - find the HEPI community

Navigate to the [HEPI community](#) (which is part of the [EU Open Research Repository](#))
Click '[New upload](#)' to create a new entry.

The screenshot shows the Zenodo website interface. At the top, the Zenodo logo is on the left, and a menu icon is on the right. Below the header, there is a search bar with the text "Health Economics for Policy Impact" and a green checkmark. Underneath, it says "Part of EU Open Research Repository" and "University of Bergen". A URL "https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101188490" is also visible. A green "New upload" button is on the right. Below the search bar, there are navigation links: "Records", "Requests", "Members", and "Settings".

In the center, a message says "We couldn't find any matches for your search". Below this is a blue "Start over" button. A "ProTip!" box contains the text: "metadata.publication_date:[2017-01-01 TO *] will give you all the publications from 2017 until today. For more tips, check out our search guide for defining advanced search queries."

At the bottom, there is a blue footer with navigation links: "About", "Blog", "Help", "Developer s", "Contribute", and "Funded by". There are also logos for CERN, OpenAIRE, and the European Union.

Step 3 - Create an upload

You can save the upload anytime as a draft and continue later. You can also preview the entry at any time.

When you are finished submit your upload for review by clicking 'submit for review' on the right hand side.

Step 3.1 - Upload files

Upload your files to the entry via drag and drop. Files cannot be changed afterward without making a new version. The old files will remain publicly accessible.

Try to choose a meaningful file name e.g. starting with a date in ISO format and a brief description afterwards. Try to avoid spaces. Read more about file naming in the [RDMkit](#).

[Open file formats](#) are preferred and will be [checked in this repository](#). If you want to share e.g. a presentation, it might be good to share the original format (e.g. pptx), an odp and pdf for interoperability.

Also ensure that you have sufficient rights to the material in order to publish it.

Files

Storage available 1 out of 100 files 0 bytes out of 50.00 GB

Preview	Filename	Size	Progress
	2025-06-14_demo_presentation.pdf md5:d41d8cd98f00b204e9800998ecf8427e		100%

Drag and drop files - or - [Upload files](#)

File addition, removal or modification are not allowed after you have published your upload.

Basic information

Digital Object Identifier

Do you already have a DOI for this upload? Yes, I already have one No, I need one

[Copy/paste your existing](#) [Get a DOI now!](#)

Reserve a DOI by pressing the button (so it can be included in files prior to upload). The DOI is registered when your upload is published.

Resource type

Presentation

Title

Draft

[Save draft](#) [Preview](#)

[Submit for review](#)

[Share](#)

Visibility

Files only

Public Restricted

Public
The record and files are publicly accessible.

Options

Apply an embargo
Record or files protection must be restricted to apply an embargo.

Step 3.2 - Mint a DOI

On the same page:

Answer 'No, I need one' to the question 'Do you already have a DOI for this upload'.

Click the 'Get a DOI now!' button.

This will be the persistent identifier for this version of the entry. Read more about DOIs on [wikipedia](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Digital_object_identifier). The DOI is reserved from now on, so you can also include it in manuscripts, etc.

Step 3.3 - Pick a resource type

On the same page:

Pick a fitting resource type. We suggest 'Presentation' for slides decks and 'Lesson' for writing accompanying your teaching/training.

Step 3.4 - Pick a title

On the same page:

Choose a title for the entry. This could be for instance: "Teaching material for XYZ in health economy"

Presentation

Title

+ Add titles

Publication date

2025-07-14

In case your upload was already published elsewhere, please use the date of the first publication. Format: YYYY-MM-DD, YYYY-MM, or YYYY. For intervals use DATE/DATE, e.g. 1939/1945.

Creators

+ Add creator

Description

Paragraph B I (t) [Icons]

+ Add description

Licenses

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International
The Creative Commons Attribution license allows re-distribution and re-use of a licensed work on the condition that the creator is appropriately credited. [Read more](#)

Edit Remove

+ Add standard + Add custom

Copyright

Copyright (C) 2025 The Authors.

A copyright statement describing the ownership of the uploaded resource.

Recommended information

Draft

Save draft Preview

Submit for review

Share

Visibility

Files only

Public Restricted

Public
The record and files are publicly accessible.

Options

Apply an embargo
Record or files protection must be restricted to apply an embargo.

Step 3.5 - Change the publication date (Optional)

On the same page:

You can change the publication date, for instance if the material was already published elsewhere before.

Step 3.6 - Add creators

On the same page:

Please enter everyone who has been part of creating the material. Adding an persistent ID such as an ORCID for each contributor is required. You can also optionally add contributors further down, for example people who have supported the process but have not contributed directly to the resource.

Add creator

Person Organization

Search for persons by name, identifier, or affiliation...

Family name *

Family name

Given names

Given names

Identifiers

e.g. ORCID, ISNI or GND.

Affiliations

Search or create affiliation

Role

Select role

✕ Cancel

✓ Save and add another

✓ Save

Step 3.7 - Add metadata

On the same page:

Provide a short description, this could be the abstract of the entry.

Provide a license for the entry. The default is [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International](#) (CC-BY 4.0). This is in line with the [Open science in Horizon Europe criteria](#). A possible alternative would be the more open [CC0 license](#).

Please enter keywords. Zenodo has inbuilt support for different controlled vocabularies and ontologies including [MeSH terms](#).

We suggest adding a term from the controlled vocabulary and add more specific keywords where necessary. The directly supported controlled vocabularies will be suggested while you are typing. If you know a term (e.g. MeSH) already you would like to use, type or copy it into the respective field.

MeSH has 500 terms regarding Health Care Economics and Organisation. You can browse this [hierarchy on the Ontology Search Portal](#). The terms are organised in a hierarchical way, so you can explore them through their hierarchy. It is not required (but possible) to include terms that are higher in the hierarchy than the one you have chosen.

Please also add the language of the resource and at least one date (e.g. creation)

Step 3.8 - Add funding information

Please add the correct funding information. Search for 'HEPI' in the pop up spawned by the '+Add' button.

The grant number for HEPI is '101188490'

If necessary you can add multiple grants and funders. You can supply funders and grants that are not searchable through the '+Add custom' dialogue.

This is important so that the entry is correctly indexed later by [CRIS systems](#).

Add standard award/grant

- HEPI — Health Economics for Policy Impact**
European Commission
- Health-Professional Education Partnership Initiative (HEPI) - Kenya**
National Institutes of Health
- Health-professional Education Partnership Initiative - Transforming Ugandan Institutions Training Against HIV/AIDS (HEPI-TUITAH)**
National Institutes of Health
- PFI: Universidad del Turabo Partnership for Innovations Program - Hispanic Entrepreneurial Program for Innovation (PIP/HEPI)**
National Science Foundation
- Health-professional Education Partnership Initiative - Transforming Ugandan Institutions Training Against HIV/AIDS (HEPI-TUITAH)**
National Institutes of Health

Did not find your award/grant? [Add a custom award/grant.](#)

Step 3.9 - Adding additional metadata (Optional)

You can add additional cross links e.g. to related work, (text-)book, theses, journal publications, conferences, etc.

Step 4 -Submit for review

Please submit your entry for review

The entry will be checked by the HEPI community curators. There are automatic [metadata](#) and [file format checks](#) by the EU Open Research Repository.

The image shows a vertical stack of four buttons. The first two buttons, 'Save draft' and 'Preview', have a light gray background and a small icon on the left (a document with a lock and an eye, respectively). The last two buttons, 'Submit for review' and 'Share', have a blue background and a small icon on the left (an upward arrow and a share symbol, respectively).

Your entry will be curated by WP16 and you will be notified once it is published or if additional information is necessary.

The DOI will now resolve to the entry. If you want to make an update to your entry you can add a new version. The new version will have its own DOI with the version as a suffix. All versions crosslink each other and old versions will advertise the new version.